

Crime Data Analysis and Predicting Crime Hotspots using Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract:

Crime prediction is of great significance to the formulation of policing strategies and the implementation of crime prevention and control. Machine learning is the current mainstream prediction method. However, few studies have systematically compared different machine learning methods for crime prediction. Results based on the historical crime data alone suggest that the LSTM model outperformed KNN, random forest, support vector machine, naive Bayes, and convolutional neural networks. In addition, the built environment data of points of interests (POIs) and urban road network density are input into LSTM model as covariates. It is found that the model with built environment covariates has better prediction effect compared with the original model that is based on historical crime data alone. Therefore, future crime prediction should take advantage of both historical crime data and covariates..

Keywords — Machine Learning, LSTM, KNN, SVM

I. INTRODUCTION

Spatiotemporal data related to the public security have been growing at an exponential rate during the recent years. However, not all data have been effectively used to tackle real-world problems. In order to facilitate crime prevention, several scholars have developed

models to predict crime. Most used historical crime data alone to calibrate the predictive models. The research on crime prediction currently focuses on two major aspects: crime risk area prediction, and crime hotspot prediction. The crime risk area prediction, based on the relevant influencing factors of criminal activities, refers to the correlation between criminal activities and physical

environment, which both derived from the "routine activity theory". Traditional crime risk estimation methods usually detect crime hotspots from the historical distribution of crime cases, and assume that the pattern will persist in the following time periods. For example, considering the proximity of crime places and the aggregation of crime elements, the terrain risk model tends to use crime-related environmental factors and crime history data, and is relatively effective for long-term, stable crime hotspot prediction.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The focus of crime hotspot prediction is to forecast future concentration of criminal events in a geographical space. Theoretical criminology provides the necessary theoretical basis. Specifically, several related criminological theories not only provide guidance for us to understand the important influence of location factors in the formation and aggregation of criminal events, but also provide a basic mechanism for the police to use information of crime hot spots for crime prevention or control. It mainly includes routine activity theory, rational choice theory, and crime patterns theory. These three theories are generally considered as the theoretical basis of situational crime prevention. Routine activity theory was jointly proposed by Cohen and Felson in 1979, and has now been further developed through integration with other theories. This theory

believes that the occurrences of most crimes, especially predatory crimes, needs the convergence of the three elements including motivated offenders, suitable targets, and lack of ability to defend in time and space. Rational choice theory was proposed by Cornish and Clarke. The theory holds that the offender's choices in terms of location, goals, methods be explained by the rational balance of effort, risk and reward. In this paper, random forest algorithm, KNN algorithm, SVM Algorithm and LSTM algorithm are used for crime prediction. First, historical crime data alone are used as input to calibrate. The models comparison would identify the most effective model. Second, built environment data such as road network density and poi are added to the predictive model as covariates, to see if prediction accuracy can be further improved.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

Crime pattern theory integrates the routine activities theory and the rational choice theory, which more closely explains the spatial distribution of criminal events. People form "cognitive map" and "activity space" through daily activities. At the same time, potential offenders also need to use their cognitive maps and choose specific locations for crimes in a relatively familiar space. When committing a crime, the offender tends to avoid those places they don't know but to choose the places where the "criminal opportunity overlaps with cognitive space" based on their rational ability. The reason why these places

become crime hotspots is that they have the obvious characteristics of "producing" or "attracting" crime. Therefore, the environmental factors of the places need to be considered besides historical crime data for the prediction of crime hotspots.

DISADVANTAGES

- Only shows the collected crime data.
- No crime predictions and no calculation of crime hotspots.
- Less effect on crime prevention.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system, random forest algorithm, KNN algorithm, SVM algorithm and LSTM algorithm are used for crime prediction. First, historical crime data alone are used as input to calibrate the models. Comparison would identify the most effective model. Second, built environment data such as road network density and poi are added to the predictive model as covariates, to see if prediction accuracy can be further improved.

ADVANTAGES

- The system introduces the problem at a brand level, which was not considered in any of the previous studies.
- Unlike other studies that majorly focus on fake review/reviewer detection, we here focus on extremist

reviewer detection, which may not be fake. Moreover,

- The system attempts to identify "groups" instead of detecting "individual user."
- The system investigates the effect of Amazon's 2016 changes in reviewing policy and the review scenario post policy changes.
- Algorithms Used: LSTM, KNN, SVM

MODULES

- User
- Admin

DESCRIPTION OF MODULES:

User:

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before performing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user can perform some operations like POST CRIME DATA SETSSEARCH ON CRIME DATA DETAILS,VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

Admin:

In this module, the Admin has to login by using valid user name and password. After login

successful he can perform some operations such as View All Crime Data Set Details, Search Crime Details, View Prediction of Crime Hotspots, View Crime Details By Area Wise, View Crime Details By Date Wise, View Crime Ratio By SVM, View Searched Crime Ratio Results, View Crime Count Results, View Crime Found Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

V. RESULTS

VI. CONCLUSION

We developed a machine learning model through this project that can forecast flight departure delays. Logistic Regression was the most effective model. A total of 62% of the departure delays were predicted by the model. Additionally, it was shown that the departure airports had a significant impact on flight delays. This obliquely implies that the likelihood of flight delays will be higher at crowded, big airports than at lesser airports. By conducting this analysis, it will be possible to ensure that the schedules are properly handled and that the airport's operations are enhanced to prevent such delays. I

think that travelling by plane is the quickest option, and I think that speed is really important.

VII. FUTURE WORK

There is no viable solution to this challenging problem at this time. The second is the spatial resolution of the grid. Future research will assess the impact of changing grid sizes on prediction accuracy. Third, the robustness and generality of the findings of this paper needs to be tested in other study areas. Nonetheless, the findings of this research have proven to be useful in a recent hotspot crime prevention experiment by the local police department at the study size.

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